

Notes

Stability Constants of Transition Metal Complexes with Oxine and its Derivatives[†]

M. ENAMULLAH** and W. LINERT*

Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Technical University Vienna, Getreidemarkt 9, A-1060 Vienna, Austria

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The present study aims to determine the stability constants of transition metal complexes with oxine and its derivatives in 50% (v/v) dioxan-water medium.

Results and Discussion

Representative titration curves of pH vs volume of NaOH added for several titrations are shown in Fig. 1. The stability constants $\log K^M$ (Table 1) for the complexes were evaluated from the curve of $\bar{n}$ vs pL ($\bar{n}$ =average number of ligands attached per metal ion and pL =free ligand exponent). The $\bar{n}$ values were found within the range of $0.1 < \bar{n} < 0.7$ at the pH range 2.8–4.0 for Cu^{II} and 4.0–5.5 for Zn^{II} and $\log K^M$ corresponds to 1:1 metal-ligand complexes formation in both cases. Above these pH ranges, precipitation took place and hence it was not possible to extend the investigation beyond these. Obviously, at higher pH values

Fig. 1. Titration curves. (◇) free acid, (Δ) free acid + ligand (2-Me-8-HQ), (□) free acid + ligand (2-Me-8-HQ) + Cu^{II} ions, and (□) free acid + ligand (2-Me-8-HQ) + Zn^{II} ions; Temp. = 30° and $I = 0.1 M$ in 50% (v/v) dioxan-water.

[†] Dedicated to Professor V. Gutmann on the occasion of his 70th birthday.

** On leave of absence from the Chemistry Department, Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Ligand	Ionic strength M	Temp. °C	pK_{NH}	pK_{OH}	$\log K^M$ (Cu)	$\log K^M$ (Zn)
2-M-8-HQ	0	30	4.54*	11.75*	12.26*	—
	0.1		4.80	11.60	12.04	9.44
	0.2		4.96	11.53	11.89	—
	0.3	35	5.08	11.45	11.80	—
	0.1		4.76	11.47	11.84	9.40
	0.1		4.70	11.38	11.68	9.35
8-HQ	0.1	30	4.65	11.23	11.5	—
	0.1		4.22	11.12	13.18	9.53

*Thermodynamic stability constants.

coordinated H_2O -ligands dissociate protons resulting in oligomeric species whose solubility is strongly reduced. It is seen from Table 1 that the $\log K^M$ value gradually decreases with increasing ionic strength at constant temperature suggesting that the ligand is interacting with metal ions in both the dissociated and associated forms. The thermodynamic stability constant for Cu^{II} , $\log K_{1=0}^M$ at zero ionic strength (I) was obtained by extrapolating the linear plots of $\log K^M$ vs $\sqrt{I}$. The stability constants (Table 1) exhibit relatively high stability of metal-ligand chelates. It appears that aromatic ring system and tertiary nitrogen of the ligand are responsible for the observed high stability of the metal chelates. The $\log K^M$ value for 2-Me-8-HQ system is lower than that for 8-HQ. This may be due to the presence of the electron-donating methyl group making the N and O atoms more basic. As a result, they bind protons more easily and strongly than the unsubstituted species and show relatively low tendency for complexation with metal ions. The presence of the methyl group near the donor atom might also have some steric influence making the complex comparatively less stable, although this effect appears to be rather small. Moreover, as the ionic potential of Cu^{II} is larger than that of Zn^{II} , the stability constant will follow the same order, which in fact is evident from the Table 1.

The stability constants decrease with increasing temperatures at constant ionic strength (Table 1),

indicating that the complexation reaction is exothermic yielding negative values of ΔH^0 . The ΔG^0 value for the Cu^{II} -complex is higher than that for the Zn^{II} -complex. The enthalpy value is larger in the Cu^{II} -complex, whereas the entropy change is more pronounced in the Zn^{II} -complex. The ΔG^0 values are negative while ΔS^0 are found to be positive (Table 2) showing that the complexation processes are thermodynamically favourable.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF METAL-LIGAND COMPLEXATION*. $I=0.1 M$, temp. = 40° . $\Delta G^0_{I=0}$ HAS BEEN EXTRAPOLATED TO IONIC STRENGTH OF $I=0M$

System	$\Delta G^0_{I=0}$ kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔG^0 kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH^0 kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS^0 kcal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-2-M-8-HQ}$	-16.99	-16.78	-13.60	10.13
$\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}\text{-2-M-8-HQ}$	—	-13.40	-3.72	30.90

* $\Delta G^0_{I=0}$ extrapolated to zero ionic strength.

The ΔG^0 and ΔH^0 values were separated into their respective electrostatic (ΔG^0_e and ΔH^0_e) and non-electrostatic (ΔG^0_c and ΔH^0_c) components as suggested by Degischer and Nancollas¹. The comparison of electrostatic and non-electrostatic parts of the thermodynamic parameters (Table 3) for the equilibrium, $\text{M}(\text{II}) + \text{L} \rightleftharpoons \text{M}(\text{II})\text{L}$, indicates that for Cu^{II} the covalent part ($\Delta G^0_c = 15.31 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) is significantly more negative than the electrostatic part ($\Delta G^0_e = 3.96 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) value, suggesting that the covalent forces are stronger than the electrostatic forces in 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -chelates. For Zn^{II} , however, ΔG^0_c ($-8.51 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) is slightly more negative than the corresponding ΔG^0_e ($-7.37 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) value showing enhanced effect of electrostatic forces in the Zn^{II} -chelates compared to that of the Cu^{II} . This is in agreement with the fact the Cu^{2+} ions are considered to be less hard electron-pair acceptors than Zn^{2+} ions.

TABLE 3—ELECTROSTATIC AND NON-ELECTROSTATIC COMPONENTS OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR 1 : 1 METAL CHELATES FORMATION

$I=0.1 M$, temp. = 40°

System	Electrostatic		Cratic	
	ΔG^0_e kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH^0_e kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔG^0_c kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH^0_c kcal mol ⁻¹
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-2-M-8-HQ}$	-3.97	1.70	-15.31	-15.31
$\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}\text{-2-M-8-HQ}$	-8.51	3.65	-7.38	-7.39

Based on the above results we performed a MM2-force-field optimisation of the geometry² for the 1 : 1 complex which resulted in the structure given in Fig. 2. Octahedral coordination has been

assumed according to the usual behavior of such Cu-system. The possible steric hindrance of the methyl group, which has been found at the complex formation constants, becomes obvious from this. So the above results further support the octahedral character of the complex.

Fig. 2. Structure of $\text{Cu}(\text{2-Me-8-HQ})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$ as result ng from MM2-optimisation.

Experimental

pH-titration technique followed was the same as described before^{3,4}. The ligand 8-hydroxyquinoline (8-HQ) and 2-methyl-8-hydroxyquinoline (2-Me-8-HQ) were used with metal ions Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} . All chemicals used were either of B.D.H. or Merck. An inert atmosphere was maintained by bubbling nitrogen gas through the reaction mixture during titration. Stability constants $\log K^M$ of complex formation were calculated from potentiometric measurements using Calvin-Bjerrum⁵ method as modified by Irving and Rossotti³.

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